

AS A PERSPECTIVE ON THE ORGANIZATION AND MANAGEMENT OF STUDENT-CENTERED LEARNING FEATURES THAT ARE CONSIDERED IMPORTANT TO CHOOSE**Ibrahimov F.***Sheki branch of ADPU, doctor of pedagogical sciences, professor
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<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8944-3611>***Abstract**

In the article, the training process is viewed as the process of education implementation, and the concept of "system" is referred to in its interpretation. Since the main goal of education is the component of "cultivating an independent and creative thinking citizen and personality", student-orientation is considered as an emergent feature of the educational system. It is chosen as a point of view that in the process of scientific cognition, it is possible to bring them closer by waiting for the existing ratio of formal and dialectical logic in the process of learning. Many interrelated and complementary factors determine that ratio. Those factors are closely related to the essence of training. In terms of the ratio of formal and dialectical logic, two ways of bringing the learning process closer to the process of scientific cognition related to management are highlighted: 1) The way to include the student in the learning process as a subject who uses the forms and regularities of formal and dialectical logic by controlling his activity; 2) The way of using forms and methods of logic as a didactic tool in the interpretation of educational material. Based on the presented position, the authors of the research paper consider it a reasonable option to implement the learning process as an interactive learning process - "a process based on interaction and activity". The learning processes focused on in the article (different based learning models) are interpreted as the "small" processes contained in the perfect learning process (the "big" process). Thanks to such a logical approach, the characteristics that are considered important to choose as a point of view in the organization and management of student-oriented training are clarified.

Keywords: training; student-oriented (interactive) training; interactive learning environment; a process based on interaction and action; decision making; problem solving; independent learning; cooperation; work in a team; intellectual, emotional and natural feelings of curiosity; logic of the subject; analytical and heuristic activity; structure; subsystem; formal and dialectical logic.

Relevance of the research topic. It is known that the goal, which is a motor model, is a system-creating component. The training process, which is the way of implementing education, is also a system, and the goal of that system (the development process conditioned by the development of human culture existing in the dialectical unity of teaching and learning processes) is to turn the learner as a stakeholder into the subject of the expected result, that is, the targeted skills should have a "space" for themselves as the personal qualities of the student. At present, in accordance with the challenges of the IV industrial revolution, the highest requirement (component) among the goals in the process of education implementation is "educating an independent and creative thinking citizen and personality". Therefore, the theory and technology of the formation of the perfect system of the training process, which aims to "educate an independent and creative thinking citizen and personality", should be clear. In other words, such a training system should be formed so that the student who takes part in that system has the opportunity to "grow as an independent and creative thinking citizen and personality" at the level corresponding to his potential. From the analysis of the scientific sources and the summarization of the collected materials, it is clear that the characteristics considered important for the selection of the student-oriented (interactive) training system as a point of view in the organization and management of the relevant goal have not been revealed,

there are theoretical and technological shortcomings, which has a negative impact on the efficiency of the educational implementation process. Despite the mentioned, we claim the relevance of the topic "Characteristics that are considered important to choose as a point of view in the organization and management of student-oriented training", and we consider conducting research in this direction to be a necessary and useful work.

Interpretation of generalizations based on information obtained on the basis of research. As is known, training is one of the main concepts of pedagogy. Pedagogical psychology has widely used this concept since its inception and has investigated the psychological problems of education in various directions. In educational psychology, the concept of "educational activity of students" was formed and established. In the school experience, this concept gained the right to citizenship. Training is an important characteristic of educational activity (it should be noted that it does not cover all its aspects). Training, in the broadest sense of the word, involves the acquisition of new knowledge, skills and habits. It should also be emphasized that learning and teaching activities are essentially different events. Learning is an integral part not only of the learning process, but of every field of activity (for example, play or work). Educational activity is a type of activity, a unique form of social activity of the personality. [5; 150]

"Education of an independent and creative thinking citizen and personality", which is included as a component in the main goal of Education, established in the "Law of the Republic of Azerbaijan on Education" [1; 9], the understanding of the task of education as a way of implementation makes it necessary for the main component of education (the student) to actively join this process, to participate in the exchange of ideas and to solve problems, which tasks (verbs) are conditioned by the challenges of the modern era. In order to be successful in modern times, it is not enough to have only knowledge of reading, writing, mathematics and natural sciences, and it is required to demonstrate more competencies. The development of information communication technologies leads to an abundance of information in society, which requires independent learning skills [10]. In order to live and move forward in a rapidly changing and developing world, a modern person needs decision making, problem solving, independent learning, cooperation, working in a team, valuing different approaches, proposing new ideas, taking initiative, etc. should be able to stand at the subject level of skills [8]. This creates conditions for sustainability for the future development of society. Therefore, we consider the usefulness of the student-oriented way of sharing human experience in the educational space, which is established adequate to the development characteristics of the modern civilization stage where the IV industrial revolution was established, as one of the undeniable options for the realization of those tasks. We accept that in the learning process, which is a way of implementing education according to modern trends, learning should be carried out by interactive methods (the term "interactive learning (or training) process" is used in the sense of "a process based on interaction and activity"). [10-11]

The interpretation of the theoretical basis of the concept of interactive learning has taken place in scientific sources. It is emphasized that this approach is related to the "Social development" theory, which is based on the formation of students' understanding of the issues they are studying. Learning is the process of making meaning. During learning, students deepen and expand existing knowledge and understanding. For this reason, competent teaching activates students, provides them with learning environments and opportunities, interactions, tasks and instructions for deep learning. [6; 59]

By the way, let's emphasize that according to the "Social development" theory, learning mainly takes place on the basis of social relations (communication) with the teacher or fellow students. Through scaffolding tasks, students can be developed by providing guidance and support, while providing feedback as a means of formative assessment. The famous social constructivist LS Vygotsky used the concept of Zone of Near Development in this regard [12].

Contrary to the idea that "education follows and adapts to development", Vygotsky pointed out the decisive role of education and upbringing in the mental development of the child, showing that well-organized education goes ahead of the child's mental develop-

ment. Training leads to the formation of immature mental functions [3; 11]. Taking into account that the correct determination of the interaction of training and mental development depends on the precise determination of the structural components of training, L.S.Vygotsky paid special attention to working out the concept of the structure of training and did substantial work in this field. He discovered that it is possible to acquire knowledge, skills and habits and to acquire general qualities and abilities (abstraction, generalization, arbitrariness). L.S.Vygotsky named the first aspect (acquisition of knowledge, skills and habits) as training (learning), and the second as development. According to him, the main subject of learning in education is the experience of knowledge and culture [9; 52]. Psychologists and pedagogues D.C.Elkonin [21], V.V.Davydov [14], L.V.Zankov [16] and others have developed L.S.Vygotsky's idea and experimentally proved that it is possible to accelerate children's development by improving the content and methods of training.

The relationship between training and various psychological categories and the points that arise in this context are among the issues in the focus of scientists' attention. Based on the information we have obtained from scientific sources and our experience, we would like to note the following conclusion: just as children's psychological development depends to a certain extent on training activities, the success of training also depends on taking into account the level of children's psychological development. From this two-way process, it is clear once again that taking into account mental aspects in training, its management, and the organization of teaching is of special importance. It follows from this that the relationship between learning activity and mental processes, especially the relationship between the learning of learning materials and students' ability to master, should be the basis of learning management work.

Certain directions for creating an interactive learning environment have also been determined by experts. Among them, the following also took place: encouraging the student to be involved in the lesson; asking questions that encourage students to answer, discuss and practice; the use of educational tools that attract the attention of students and encourage them to respond; creating a working group atmosphere in the classroom; the involvement of the teacher along with the students.[6;60]

Many studies show that one of the keys to effective learning is the activation of natural curiosity. It is not accidental that the concept of feelings of natural curiosity was added to the classification of popular intellectual and emotional feelings. Natural curiosity raises questions, and questions lead us to search for answers, and this search leads to the acquisition of new knowledge and skills, and thus to the spiritual transformation of the world. When systematically solving such an important problem as the development of thinking in modern schoolchildren, the question arises. After all, the question is directly about the development of thinking, the development of thought. In the dialogue pro-

cess, the teacher's judgment style, the skill of formulating questions, are effective thinking lessons for logical students. It is an indisputable fact that when the structure, functions and causes of the studied objects and phenomena are explained with the dimensions of theoretical thinking, the conditions for the formation of logical questions are automatically created in the students. Emotional activation of students in class is also an important condition for formulating student questions. Although the question is genetically formed in the warm breath of feelings, it has always reflected the light of thinking. In the process of teaching separate subjects, the development of the system of activating the cognitive activity of students in the direction of questions attracts more attention as an important psychological, pedagogical and methodical problem.

There is no doubt that the strong development of science requires a comprehensive study of the scientific research process. The level of human development has increased so much that the problems facing people require creative activity. A free personality should be able to meet such demands, and reality should be taken into account in solving the problems of preparing students for life.

However, human creative activity is a complex dialectical process and this process is uncontrollable, there is no general way of logical formalization of creativity, there is only a logical system of any specific discovery [7].

The contradiction between the need to formalize human creative activity and its uncontrollability is clearly understood. One of the main ways to solve this conflict is to find ways to manage the development of students' creative abilities.

The need for students to participate in the learning process using the forms and methods of dialectical logic does not mean to completely equate that process with the process of scientific research. The formal and dialectical logic characteristic of the entire scientific understanding is the basis of ready giving of knowledge and obtaining it through search in the training process.

In science, the research method and results are given in accordance with the logically arranged movement of human thought, developed in a strict logical sequence. The orderly way of the thought towards the truth, explained in scientific knowledge, also appears before us as the form and laws of formal logic. There is no doubt that there is a difference between the process of discovery and the development of a logical system of the path of discovery and its consequences. The strict logical sequence of thinking principles, methods and operations leading to ready results, laws and rules does not reflect the true sequence of thinking principles, methods and operations carried out during the discovery of the truth. In the head of each researcher, the thought process related to the research may resemble a generalized logical conclusion. The way to achieve the result continues due to psychological and social factors. The sequence, sequence and nature of interaction of induction and deduction, analysis and synthesis principles and means existing in the logic of discovery depends on the unique activity of intuition in one or another specific case and can be very complex.

It is known that the concept, law, principle, etc. acquired in the course of the historical development of the relevant science. preserves the structure and logic of science as much as possible under the condition of taking into account the sequence, past and present results of science and the possibility of students learning them. In accordance with the purpose of the training, it includes the main concepts, facts, theories, laws, terms, as well as methods of operation. The logic of the subject corresponds to the invariant logic of science. The logic of the subject, in turn, has a determining role in determining the logic of the learning process. However, it is not correct to equate the logic of science with the logic of science. The difference between them is determined by a number of objective and subjective criteria. Textbooks are prepared on the basis of invariant knowledge of the content of science, where the logic of obtaining this or that scientific knowledge in the research process is formed. The goals of the training process are implemented in the way (depending on the teacher) the correlation between the logic of the subject and the real level of the students, and the regulation of this relationship by the teacher. Here, also, the development of students' creative abilities and independence is solved depending on the interaction and regulation mentioned in the problem. [9; 45-46].

The logic of the training process is determined by objective and subjective criteria, it is dynamic in nature. There is no unanimity in views on the logical understanding of this process, which has very complex characteristics. For example, M.A.Danilov distinguishes between the logic of the learning process and the logic of the teaching subject, but also notes that there is a close connection between them [14; 17].

M.I. According to Makhmutov, it is necessary to take into account the logic of teaching and teaching material, which are the main components of the training process. Without taking into account the logic of teaching, the logic of training cannot be imagined, otherwise we are talking about the logic of the student's cognitive activity.[13; 100-101].

B.A.Ahmadov writes: "The logic of training is such a series of teaching steps that ensure the acquisition of the student's knowledge and the development of his mental powers: what amount of material to give to which student, how to ask questions to whom, what to teach in class, what to assign at home, etc. ...the logic of training consists of the interaction between the logic of the subject and the real levels of students, the regulation of this relationship by the teacher. The logic of training reflects the relationship between the teacher, the teaching material and the student"[4; 126-127].

According to the formalized logic of the acquisition of truths, the staticity existing in the subject and the corresponding teaching material, which differs in its specific characteristics, but retains this formality, is brought to a dynamic state by teacher-student relations. The student's acquisition of knowledge does not take place only in the form of forms and laws of formal logic, but in dialectical forms and regularities. This dialectic unity is regulated and facilitated by the teacher in accordance with the set goal. By the way, let's em-

phasize that "in modern education, the teacher's approach is facilitation, that is, he does not give information ready, but encourages the student to learn, teaches them the way to learn, forms metacognitive knowledge and skills, directs them to solve the problem effectively, in a word, scaffolding" [6; 68]. Facilitator teacher creates an effective learning environment, ensures emotional, intellectual, physical and psychological development of students. It also determines the potential of students and applies effective methods to develop students in this area.

It is possible to bring them closer together by waiting for the existing ratio of formal and dialectical logic in the process of scientific cognition. Many interrelated and complementary factors determine that ratio. Those factors are closely related to the essence of training. In terms of the ratio of formal and dialectical logic, two ways of bringing the learning process closer to the process of scientific cognition are distinguished in relation to management: 1) The way to include the student in the learning process as a subject who uses the forms and regularities of formal and dialectical logic by controlling his activity; 2) The way of using forms and methods of logic as a didactic tool in the interpretation of educational material.

The student's entry into the learning process as a subject who manages his learning activity based on the forms and regularities of formal and dialectical logic enables him to perform the function of "researcher". Undoubtedly, when a student performs the function of a researcher in the learning process, the course of his thought process does not coincide with the thought process of a scientist who is directed to a new discovery in the process of scientific research. However, psychological aspects have a special role in both of these processes, and the structure of cognitive activity in both processes is determined by the problem. It is important for the teacher to know the structure of one or another type of mental activity in the organization of the teaching and cognitive process, which differs from the search for the problem.

What is discussed here is directly related to the topic we are focusing on research. Thus, depending on the content of the problem, the degree of difficulty for each student, the development of his mental abilities, the ability to solve the problem, the thinking process can take place in an analytical and heuristic structure. The structure of the heuristic type of mental activity is fundamentally different. Here we are talking about non-discursive thinking (not based on formal logical conclusions) and it is applied in the search for a solution to this problem. Non-discursive thinking (problem, assumption, reasoning, hypothesis) opens a wide opportunity to manage the process of development of the student's mental abilities. In the search for a solution in the structure of the analytical type of mental activity, the application of known solution algorithms (or the search for a new analytical way) is used. This type of mental activity can play an important role in the realization of the goals set for the training process [6; 46-52].

In accordance with the formalized way of intellectual action in the process of acquiring knowledge, two ways are chosen for explaining the learning material:

the first way is that the learning material is interpreted with reference to the exact sequence of mental activity and all the rules of logical thinking based on the formalized logic of knowledge acquisition. The interpretation of the learning material according to the formal logic leads to the intellectual activity of the student of a reproductive nature. In this case, the student mainly acquires knowledge ready (such a way has existed in human experience and its existence is inevitable; the role of the process of transmission of human experience from generation to generation in the existence of the civilization process is undeniable!). The second way is characterized by problem-search.

In teaching practice, in most cases, the dialectical way of scientific understanding is opened by the teacher, the results obtained by the forms, principles and laws of formal logic are analyzed and followed in thinking. In this process, the student follows the movement of thought based on the laws of formal and dialectical logic. In fact, in this process, the student gets an opportunity to get acquainted with someone else's intellectual activity and its results.

When using both ways, of course, reference is made to the logical analysis of the subject, the development of students and the laws of logic. In other words, when the limitations of the student's ability to perform creative activities independently are determined, the teaching material is interpreted by the teacher by referring to the laws of formal and dialectical logic, using its forms and methods as tools.

Studying the logical problem of training is a requirement of practice. The change of the tasks of the school (in fact, more correct definition) has made the search for ways to develop students' thinking more urgent, and at the same time, it has become necessary to study the logic of education. Development of students' logical thinking abilities occupies an important place among the problems of education. To prove or disprove the truth of any reasoning, summarize and abstract, analyze and hypothesize, come to conclusions, etc. in the acquisition of knowledge. such skills are of particular importance. The development of logical thinking facilitates the assimilation of large amounts of knowledge. Therefore, the issue of the development of students' logical thinking is related to the logic of the learning process and is a problem that needs to be solved.

The regularities defined by formal logic, which reflect some features of thinking, should be considered as the logical basis of the management of the learning process. In the process of solving this or that issue, as new ideas, concepts, judgments, new productions and results of new thinking are formed, logical relations between them are determined. On the basis of those determined logical relations, another judgment is made in the form of mental conclusions. On the basis of logical forms of thinking, the student learns the relations between objects and phenomena of reality, their properties and signs, acquires knowledge and methods of action expressed in concepts and categories in a formal way. In this process, the student has the opportunity to carry out elementary formal logical operations, gets experience of mental activity. Pupils learn from judg-

ments in two ways: a) indirectly (as a judgment is a direct expression of what is perceived) and b) indirectly (through mental conclusions and considerations - without formalizing here, from inductive (induction) and deductive (deduction) types of mental conclusions uses) benefits.

During the training process, work is not done, and cannot be done, only with ready-made forms, according to the requirements of the tasks set in front of him. Here, the concrete conditions under which concepts, judgments, and mental results are created cannot be put into the background.

Summarizing what has been said, it can be concluded that the expectation of the logic of training (necessary for the achievement of successful results in the training process, the result is ensured by the teaching steps and their sequence) from the logic of the taught subject (formalized knowledge and methods of action in the teaching material, leading to the correct result without deviations) it is to focus on the result depending on the system of conducting and outputting), the intellectual capabilities of the students, the level of preparation and professionalism of the teacher, and other conditions that may affect the training process (for example, the material base, infrastructure, etc.). The logical bases of training and their expectation determine the optimal reconciliation of analytical and heuristic types of students' mental activity, and make this process, which is considered as a way of implementing education, student-oriented (interactive).

By the way, let's emphasize that scientific sources contain information about student-oriented (interactive) learning "approaches (models)". These include inquiry and inquiry-based learning, problem-based learning, project-based learning approaches, etc. student-oriented (interactive) approaches take place. In fact, student-orientation (focusing the interactivity-process on the interested party component-the student) is the main feature of the new educational system, which is considered as a way of implementing education formed according to the challenges of the IV industrial revolution, its emergent nature. Based on the emergent nature of the perfect training system, the mentioned approaches can be transformed in this system and exist with the function of subsystem, part, element (from this point of view, we refer the perfect training system to the class of "open systems"; it should not be forgotten that the transformed ones are also "systems" " can be interpreted with the concept, and here it is appropriate to recall SASHaporinsky's scientific interpretation of the relationship between "big" and "small" processes ("big" process (system) contains "small" processes (systems): "big" process "small" " is not a simple sum of processes [20]. The learning process consists of "big" and "small" processes. In our opinion, the scientific cognitive process is the whole process of learning Problem-based learning acts as a subsystem of the student's learning activity. The system represented by the concept of "inquiry-based learning" is a "small" system of the educational process. Thus, in the learning process, students are involved in investigative activities by asking questions, proposing hypotheses (justified hypotheses), observing, conducting research, drawing

conclusions, and verifying the results. This activity in itself provides an opportunity to develop various skills (goal determination, time and priority management, information processing, problem solving, teamwork, written and oral communication, criticism, evaluation, etc.). Summarizing research on inquiry and inquiry-based learning, its main components can be listed as follows: orientation; posing the main question or putting forward a hypothesis; investigation; result; discussion. Cognitive activity of students in problematic learning is analyzed, first of all, as a thinking process, it is investigated in a procedural direction. For the problem-based learning concept, thinking is a process with complex patterns. According to this concept, the learning process is structured not by the laws of memory, which are understood and evaluated unilaterally, but by the laws of the complex, multifaceted thinking process itself. In the architecture of the process, those regularities are linked in one occasion-problem root. Identifying the problem, formulating the problem, solution of the problem-in the lesson, it is precisely at this root that a strange space of thought arises in the course of the own laws of thinking; the student searches, searches, discovers something new, in this process he does not just think, his thought and thinking develops and gradually acquires new merits [6].

In our opinion, Project and Problem-based learning, which can be included in the Excellent learning system, are "small" processes with Student-Centered (student-centered) characteristics, which both have common characteristics in terms of creating learning activity, developing critical thinking, problem-solving, and cooperation in students. One point to note is that both Project and Problem-based learning require certain background knowledge. Therefore, their application in the early learning period is less effective. Exposing students to too much information in a short amount of time while engaging in the activities mentioned can hinder quality learning. We know that it is necessary to emphasize that in project-based learning, the teacher shows his support in various forms as a facilitator. Thus, he is closely involved in asking questions, providing resources, and giving regular feedback. No matter how much the teacher's role as a facilitator in problem-based learning continues, he takes a step back and gives students freedom to choose a problem, gather information, and formulate a solution to the problem. In problem-based learning, evaluation is done in terms of the problem-solving process, critical thinking, and the quality of the proposed solution. Assessment criteria in project-based learning have complex characteristics due to the specific characteristics of the learning in question. Assessment of skills such as cooperation, creativity, and presentation should be considered both in terms of content [6; 93-94]

It should be noted that the characteristics of the "Socrates" method, which are particularly important in terms of ensuring student-centeredness, are optional. The interview focuses on the problem. The search for truth is its logic. The search for truth is not focused on the exploitation of memory, but on the activation of thinking and creative imagination.

Let's emphasize that in the history of philosophical and pedagogical thought, Socrates' interviews are considered the first methodology developed with the point of awakening thought. V.A.Konyev particularly appreciates two aspects of this unusual method - irony and doubt. It is also known that Socrates characterized his method as "maeutics, i.e. the art of midwifery: after all, he helped the birth of thought with miraculous questions. Socrates said in his reflections: "By asking you, I study the subject only together with you, because I do not know it myself". Years and years later, outstanding educators highly appreciated this quality in the teacher, and the words of A. Distverg sounded like a pedagogical aphorism: "Bad the teacher conveys the truth (to the students) in a ready manner, and a good teacher searches for it (with the students in the lesson) and finds it. How precisely these words express the creativity of both the teacher and the students in the conditions of "we appreciate"-problematic training [5 ; 79-80].

Effective provision of student-centeredness is realized when the learning environment is compatible with the active cognitive activity of all students while mobilizing their potential. This becomes real when different methods are used with students belonging to different groups (according to their learning, intelligence, learning achievements, perception, etc.) in the same class or learning environment, and lessons are planned according to each group of students. This kind of training strategy is called "Differential approach in training". Experience shows that differentiation is inevitable in an environment where there are groups (heterogeneous class) with different learning characteristics and requirements in the same space. Experienced teachers take into account that students differ in their learning speed, in this regard, tasks are assigned to students based on their comprehension potential. It should not be forgotten that differentiation is not the presentation of several additional means of activity to the student during teaching. It is necessary to know that teaching is not differentiated when the teacher assigns the same task to each student, evaluates all students by giving general feedback, applies teaching methods only to gifted students, and creates always-changing groups in the teaching process. Students' interest, level of preparation, and learning styles should be taken into account during differentiation. Differential training should be reflected in the content, process, result, evaluation components of the lesson. [6; 88-89]

By the way, let's emphasize that the taught content should meet the requirements of the substandards. However, some of the students in the classroom during teaching may not understand the content completely, some may have partially mastered it, and some may have a better understanding. Therefore, when preparing tasks, it is necessary to pay attention that these tasks correspond to the stages of Bloom's taxonomy (remembering, understanding, applying, analyzing, evaluating, creating): one of the criteria that determines the degree of difficulty of the tasks is the stages of the cognitive field.

A successful differentiated instruction strategy involves delivering content in a variety of ways. Because

of differential learning, not all students need the teacher's help to the same extent. Some students may choose to work individually, some in pairs, and some in groups. While some students develop individually with the teacher, others learn content more effectively through interaction.

Note that differentiation as a general learning strategy is similar to scaffolding. Thus, in both, the goal is to achieve the same learning result for different students, that is, to bring the student from "where he is" to the goal. Let's emphasize that the differential approach is applied in the teaching process, and scaffolding can include the entire teaching approach. Scaffolding provides a piecemeal presentation of the given material, from easy to difficult, with reference to the student's previous knowledge and skills, facilitating effective learning by someone more experienced. In differentiation, this process can be carried out without facilitation. The differential approach is a process within scaffolding. [6; 89]

The result. 1) Education is an open system that includes the dialectical unity of teaching and learning, it is a way of implementing education; 2) referring to the concept of "system" in the interpretation of the training process is of great importance in increasing and improving its efficiency, it is useful in revealing its nature, revealing the dialectic of structural elements, and eliminating mistakes that will be made in the adjustment of said dialectic; 3) Since the main goal of education is the component of "cultivating an independent and creative thinking citizen and personality", student orientation (interactivity) should be considered as an emergent sign of the education system; 4) In the process of scientific cognition, it is possible to achieve their rapprochement and improve their perfection by waiting for the existing ratio of formal and dialectical logic in the training process; 5) Many interrelated and complementary factors determine the optimal ratio of formal and dialectical logics in the learning process, which are closely related to the essence of learning; 6) In terms of the optimal ratio of formal and dialectical logic, there are two ways of bringing the learning process closer to the process of scientific cognition related to management: a) The way to include the student in the learning process as a subject who uses the forms and regularities of formal and dialectical logic by controlling his activity; b) The way of using forms and methods of logic as a didactic tool in the interpretation of educational material; 7) implementation of learning in the training process as an interactive-"a process based on interaction and activity" can be considered an acceptable option; 8) It is useful to interpret the learning processes (various based learning models) that are formed adequately to the nature of the training system as "small" processes included in the perfect learning process ("big" process), which has a positive effect on its efficiency; thanks to such a logical approach, the characteristics that are considered important to be selected as a point of view in the organization and management of student-oriented training are clarified.

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